

ASSESSING DOMESTIC IMPLICATIONS OF BELT AND ROAD INITIATIVE: A CASE STUDY OF CHINA-PAKISTAN ECONOMIC CORRIDOR (CPEC)

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Abstract

China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) – which sustains the image of a transformative project in Pakistan – provides a valuable case study to analyze how China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) could potentially impact the economic sociopolitical dynamics of the host countries. Within this context, this paper puts forth a critically oriented analysis of the first five years of CPEC and assesses whether the initiative has succeeded in fulfilling Pakistan's grand ambitions in terms of boosting its economic growth and national development goals. This paper demonstrates that in the short-term, CPEC has produced several implications detrimental to Pakistan's macroeconomic and sociopolitical stability. It reveals that the opaque and asymmetrical nature of CPEC-related decision-making and implementation process has actually revived the deep-rooted political disputes in the centre-province/inter-province relations and highlighted the ethnic tendencies in various parts of Pakistan. Additionally, the project-related cost overruns, growing import bills, ballooning trade deficit with China, and hugely unsustainable debts are some of the untoward fallouts of CPEC which – if handled wrongly – could inadvertently amplify challenges to Pakistan's economic stability. Given this, CPEC serves as an indicator for other countries to understand the potential risks that BRI might carry for their economic and political systems.

Introduction

Since its inception in October 2013, China's Belt and Road Initiative has been viewed with increasing suspiciousness around the world. Some key questions over more fundamental issues such as how BRI is shaping the political, economic, and security dynamics of host countries have drawn lively debates. In this context, China's BRI-related interactions with Pakistan can be considered as an indicator for understanding implications of Beijing's infrastructure development model/framework for the host countries. In this context, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) - the flagship or pilot project of BRI - offers a valuable case for examining the costs and implications that China's BRI framework carries for the economic and political systems of the participant countries.

In Pakistan, CPEC has been characterized as a transformative project that would stimulate a nationwide economic activity, create jobs for Pakistani youth, and help the country to achieve 7 to 8 per cent increase in its annual economic growth rate by 2030 (Dawn, September 1, 2019). The narrative that presents CPEC as a transformative project is predicated on the headline numbers of Chinese investment estimated around US\$62 billion, and the wide-ranging infrastructure development projects, including the development of energy sector,

railway and highways, seaports, and special economic zones. Regardless of the official narrative, many analysts and policy makers have raised reasonable doubts and skepticism about CPEC's potential to boost and transform Pakistan's economy. Experts have raised questions about the implications that CPEC carries for Pakistan's sociopolitical dynamics. Despite all the concerns, CPEC has completed the first of its three five-year phases. Most of the early harvest projects, both energy and infrastructure projects, have been completed and operationalized. Thus, it is perhaps the best time to examine how CPEC has performed so far. Drawing on the recent data collected from the official CPEC web-portal of the Planning Commission of Pakistan, local and international newspapers and think-tanks reports, and other primary and secondary sources, this paper puts forth a critically oriented analysis of the first five years of CPEC and assesses whether the initiative has succeeded in fulfilling Pakistan's grand ambitions in terms of boosting its economic growth and development goals. In this way, this paper adds an important dimension to the existing literature by providing insights into the latent costs and consequences that China's BRI framework might carry for the economic and political systems of the participant countries. The paper is divided into three sections. The first section provides a brief overview of CPEC

and its various components including energy projects, transportation infrastructure projects, and special economic zones (SEZs). The second section assesses the impact of CPEC on Pakistan's economy. It examines some key components and projects of CPEC, evaluates their associated costs, and examines their impact on Pakistan's macro-economic stability. The third section examines the interplay between CPEC and Pakistan's domestic political dynamics. Multiple factors are discussed and analyzed to explicate the relationship between growing provincialism, ethnic-nationalism and the politics of CPEC. Factors such as growing center-province differences over CPEC implementation and their impact on national and provincial politics and the role of CPEC in aggravating the ethnic cleavages in different provinces of Pakistan are discussed in this section. The conclusion summarizes the argument and provides some policy prescriptions to Pakistan's government to overcome the problems and challenges emerging from the introduction and implementation of CPEC.

Genesis of the CPEC

Inaugurated by Chinese President in April 2015, CPEC is one of the six economic corridors proposed under the BRI. It is regional connectivity project designed to connect China's landlocked western Xinjiang autonomous region with Pakistan's ports in the

Arabian Sea, including the Gwadar port and the Karachi port. According to the officials from China and Pakistan, "the primary objective of CPEC is to increase economic growth in Pakistan and Xinjiang in China, and to enhance trade between Gwadar port in the Arabian Sea and Kashgar in Xinjiang (Verma 2019, 10)."

The construction of CPEC has been divided into three phases; early harvest or short-term projects to be completed around 2020, medium-term projects to be completed around 2025, and long-term projects to be completed around 2030. The early harvest phase includes the construction of various energy projects, highways, rail-based public transport projects, and Gwadar port. However, the main focus of the early harvest phase is the construction of energy projects. Out of US\$62 billion CPEC outlay, approximately US\$35 billion - 74 per cent of total CPEC outlay - has been earmarked for energy projects (Afzal and Naseem 2017, 213). According to the official data available on CPEC web-portal, out of total 20 energy projects, 10 projects worth US\$10.14 billion (including US\$1.47 billion Thar-coal mine) have already been completed/operationalized and pumping 5,318MW energy to Pakistan's national grid (Planning Commission of Pakistan 2020). Additionally, 7 more energy projects worth US\$10.3 billion are under construction. In addition to the completed and under constructions energy projects, some large-scale

energy projects such as Gadani coal power project, Muzaffargarh coal power project, and Diamer-Bhasha Dam project have been shelved due to costly and non-viable commercial terms. CPEC-related infrastructure projects include the development and upgrading of overland transportation infrastructure, SEZs, Gwadar port, and fiber optic communication networks. Overall, approximately US\$12 billion has been earmarked for various infrastructure projects and SEZs. Furthermore, US\$8.1 billion has been earmarked for the construction of Pakistan Railway mainline ML-1. According to CPEC web-portal, Karakoram Highway phase-II (US\$1.31 billion), Peshawar-Karachi Motorway (US\$3.88 billion), and Lahore Orange-Line rail-based mass transit project (US\$1.62 billion) have been completed in the early harvest phase (Planning Commission of Pakistan 2020). Under CPEC portfolio, China and Pakistan have agreed to establish total 9 SEZs in different regions and provinces of Pakistan. However, little progress has been made regarding the establishment of SEZs. The early harvest phase of CPEC has been almost entirely dominated by energy projects. Out of all 9 proposed SEZs, only Allama Iqbal Industrial City, Faisalabad, has entered into the construction phase.

CPEC and its Impact on Pakistan's Economy

There is a broad consensus among Pakistan's policy-making circles that CPEC is a vital project for Pakistan's economic growth and social

development. Contrary to official claims, a careful analysis of the first five years of CPEC reveals that the initiative has underperformed and played a key role in exacerbating Pakistan's economic problems. As a starting point, CPEC-related terms and conditions provide useful insights to understand the perils that China's BRI carries for Pakistan's economy. Pakistan's officials say that previous federal government had poorly negotiated CPEC and agreed to terms that are too expensive and more favorable for Beijing's commercial interest. According to reports, the "Article-II of CPEC Framework Agreement" binds Pakistan to award project building contracts to Chinese firms and companies on preferential terms even if they offer higher prices in their bids (*The Express Tribune*, December 15, 2015).

For example, in December 2015, Chinese firms had forced Pakistan's "Public Procurement Regulatory Authority (PPRA)" to increase the cost of three infrastructure projects to US\$4.4 billion - 23 per cent higher than the initially approved prices by the PPRA (*The Express Tribune*, December 15, 2015). Initially in August 2015, these projects were approved by the PPRA at an estimated cost of US\$3.5 billion (*Dawn*, August 13, 2015). According to Pakistani officials, core reason for 'upward revision in the cost was that the contractors placed bids at higher than approved prices' (*The Express Tribune*, December 15, 2015). Moreover, in a clear

violation of PPRA rules and international procedures of open competitive bidding, the bidding for the projects was also kept confined to Chinese enterprises.

Similarly, National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA) was forced by Pakistan's federal government to increase the original tariff of CPEC-related Matiari to Lahore transmission line (worth US\$1.65 billion) from 71 paise per unit to 74 paise per unit after the Chinese contractors declined to undertake the project at the initial price (Dawn, March 12, 2017). In April 2020, an inquiry report revealed that the above-mentioned transmission line project was 234 per cent "expensive than a similar project in India with better technology (The Express Tribune, April 21, 2020)." The inquiry report also revealed that the project was awarded "through government-to-government agreement, hence, no bidding was carried out for the award of this project (The Express Tribune, April 21, 2020)."

Furthermore, to attract Chinese investment, Pakistan has offered exceptionally high rate of return on equity (ROE) for coal power plants, 34.9 per cent for Thar coal power projects and 27.2 per cent for Port Qasim, Hubco, and Sahiwal coal power plants (The Express Tribune, February 15, 2017). According to the officials from Pakistan's Ministry of Water and Power, high ROE had to be given to attract investment in coal power plants because Chinese investors

"were not ready to invest in coal-based projects (Downs 2019, 22)." Pakistan has also offered higher upfront tariffs for electricity produced by these power plants – US\$0.092 per unit price – much higher than the US\$ 0.62 per unit price that Chinese firms offered to Bangladesh in similar projects. Given this, many in Pakistan have started raising question: "what is the benefit of CPEC to the Pakistani electric power consumer? (Rafiq, 2018)."

Moreover, Chinese loan-based financing for the coal fired power plants is another important factor which has played a key role in aggravating Pakistan's macroeconomic problems. It is estimated that against "the US\$26.5 billion of CPEC inflows by 2023, Pakistan will have to repay China US\$40 billion in the form of debt repayments and return on investment over the next 20 years (Shah 2019, 424)." Furthermore, a closer look at the recent statistics from State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) reveals that since the advent of CPEC, the volume of Pakistan's external debts and liabilities has increased dramatically. Pakistan's external debt and liabilities, which stood at US\$73.94 billion in June 2016, have grown to US\$111.04 billion in December 2019 (SBP 2019, 115). Moreover, Pakistan's debt-to-gross domestic product (GDP) ratio has ballooned from 67 per cent of GDP in FY 2016-17 to 75.3 per cent of GDP in FY 2017-18 (Forbes, July 4, 2019). Likewise, Pakistan's borrowing from China, both CPEC-

related and commercial, has increased dramatically – US\$3.955 billion in fiscal year (FY) 2017, US\$4.011 billion in FY 2018 (SBP 2018, 73), and US\$4.721 in FY 2019 (SBP 2019, 86).

In addition to costly Chinese loans, the fast-track completions of CPEC projects has produced unhealthy upsurge in Pakistan's imports from China. For Pakistan, the key rationale behind the construction of a large number of coal power plants under CPEC was to reduce the country's energy related import bill (Pakistan is a net importer of liquified natural gas (LNG) and crude oil) in the long-term by increasing the share of coal in country's power generation mix (Ali, 2019, p. 102). However, the fast-track completion of CPEC-related energy projects actually caused a massive upsurge in Pakistan's imports from China, which ultimately played its part in the worsening of country's balance of payment crisis.

According to SBP statistics, Pakistan's imports from China's cement, machinery, and steel industries have markedly increased in the first five years. For instance, Pakistan imports from China arose from US\$7 billion in FY 2015 to US\$8.127 billion in FY 2016, US\$10.077 billion in FY 2017 and US\$11.457 billion in FY 2018 (SBP, 2018, p. 126). In FY 2019, Pakistan's imports from China stood at US\$10.162 billion (SBP, 2019, p. 126). A closer look at these figures reveals that Pakistan's

overall import bill from China during the first five years has swelled to more than US\$38 billion. In contrast, Pakistan's total exports to China during the same time-period have reached to US\$7.13 billion (SBP, 2019, p. 126), which means that in the first five years, Pakistan's bilateral trade deficit with China has peaked to approximately US\$30 billion mark.

For many, CPEC presents a lucrative opportunity for Pakistan to achieve rapid economic growth through infrastructure development. Yet, rapidly growing volume of external loans and fast swelling import bills have "dramatically increased the risk of Islamabad's defaulting on financial obligations to Beijing (Rehman 2019, 418)." In fact, Pakistan had already faced a serious balance of payment crisis in October 2018, when SBP announced that its foreign exchange reserves (Forex) had tumbled to a five-year lowest level of US\$7.8 billion, while the net Forex held by the commercial banks had plunged to US\$6.4 billion (Reuters, October 22, 2018). To avert the default, government of Pakistan turned to International Monetary Fund (IMF) for a bailout package for the 22nd time in its history. In 2019, IMF agreed to provide US\$6 billion bailout package to Pakistan. But despite the IMF loan deal, Pakistan's economic growth rate in 2019 plunged to 3.3 per cent – 2.2 per cent lower than what it was in 2018, fiscal deficit ballooned from 6.4 to nearly 9 per cent over the same time

period, and inflation increased to 9.41 per cent – the highest in five years (Kugelman 2019).

This situation does not bode well for Pakistan because it is required to make debt repayments of approximately US\$37 billion to both multilateral and bilateral creditors between 2019 to 2022 (The News, November 17, 2019). Out of total US\$37 billion debt repayments scheduled for 2019-2022 period, Pakistan will repay US\$14.6 billion due for US\$21.8 billion bilateral and commercial loans that Islamabad owes to China (Dawn, July 15, 2019). Given this, analysts aver that the debt-ridden CPEC infrastructure “has dramatically increased the risk of Islamabad’s defaulting on financial obligations to China (Shah 2019, 418).” Consequently, Pakistan’s President Arif Alvi, during his visit to China on March 17-18, 2020, made special request to the Chinese government to ease debt repayment of more than US\$30 billion CPEC-related loans (Dawn, April 15, 2020).

Within the context of CPEC, China’s inordinate preference to sustain its economic goals demonstrates that Pakistan need to (re)negotiate project-related terms and conditions in a way that it could draw outcomes more favorable to its economic and commercial interests. Malaysia’s renegotiation of a BRI-related railway project can be taken as a prime example in this regard. Facing the danger of cost overruns and concerns over growing project-

related debts, Malaysia had originally suspended the railway project when its finance ministry estimated that the cost overruns will increase the project price from US\$16 billion to US\$20 billion (*The Washington Post*, August 21, 2018). Later in April 2019, a renegotiated deal between China and Malaysia brought down the project cost from US\$20 billion to US\$10.7 billion (*Bloomberg*, April 12, 2019). Similarly, Myanmar also scaled-down a BRI-related project from initial cost of US\$7.5 billion to US\$1.3 billion on the grounds that “Myanmar didn’t want to repeat the experience of other countries and build infrastructure without sufficient demand” (*Nikkei Asian Review*, September 28, 2018).

Impact of CPEC on the Domestic Politics of Pakistan

As discussed above, the government of Pakistan has repeatedly portrayed CPEC as a transformative project that will accrue benefits for all provinces of Pakistan. But due to “asymmetries among political decision-making powers (federal government vs. regions) and an unequal distribution of both national wealth and investments (Wolf 2020, 90)”, CPEC has been received with increasing skepticism in different parts of the country particularly in Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) and Gilgit Baltistan (GB) region. The interplay of CPEC with Pakistan’s domestic politics has already triggered many controversies in centre-province relations with federating units

objecting to the federal government's highly centralized decision-making approach in terms of CPEC implementation plans and distribution of economic resources.

The centre-versus-province and inter-province tensions over the highly centralized CPEC-related decision-making, implementation process, and distribution of investments reflects a historical fracture or division between the federation of Pakistan and federating units. The history of the federation of Pakistan has been marked by continuous tensions in centre-province relations and inter-province tussles over centralization of power and demands for equal distribution of resources (Adeney 2012; Siddiqi 2012; Shah 2014; Mengal 2016). Within the context of CPEC, smaller provinces especially Balochistan, KP and GB region have repeatedly accused the previous PML-N led federal government of prioritizing Punjab province in the allocation of CPEC projects (especially in relation to SEZs and transportation infrastructure projects) for gaining electoral benefits (Rifaat and Maini 2016, 15).

In the context of electoral politics, the PML-N draws majority of its support from its constituencies in Punjab. Moreover, Punjab's 54 per cent seats in Pakistan's National Assembly gives the province a dominant role in determining that which political party will form the government in the centre (Adeney 2015, 11).

Given the importance of Punjab's large number of seats in the National Assembly, the previous PML-N led federal government tactically decided to make Punjab the epicenter of CPEC. Several "key projects were located in the PML-N-run Punjab province, or even sponsored by the PML-N-run provincial government and personally directed by the chief minister, Shahbaz Sharif (Rafiq 2019, p. 238)." As Pakistan's general elections approached in 2018, major opposition political parties, particularly Imran Khan and his party PTI, focused criticism on PML-N for not only disproportionately allocating majority of CPEC resources to Punjab but also for cutting opaque and unfavorable CPEC deals with China. As a matter of fact, PTI's criticism of PML-Ns CPEC approach led PTI to win the general elections in July 2018 (Schwelmein 2019, 254). After assuming the office of Prime Minister, Imran Khan attempted to renegotiate CPEC deals struck by previous PML-N led federal government but failed due to Pakistan's dependence on Chinese loans to avert an impending economic crisis and the lack of political leverage over Beijing because of the growing fissures in Islamabad's relations with the US (Reuters, September 30, 201).

Although CPEC has been projected as a transformative national project that that will equally benefit all the provinces (Saleem 2017, 119), for smaller provinces like Balochistan, CPEC appears to be another exploitative deal -

“unlikely to offer them economic development or new social welfare benefits commensurate with its costs, which were likely to include population displacement and environmental degradation (Markey 2020a).” Since the inception of CPEC in 2015, Baloch people have been complaining that despite being the key node in CPEC, Balochistan is not getting the equal share in the initiative. Official statistics available on CPEC web portal confirm that apart from the Gwadar port project (which actually was launched well before the announcement of CPEC), Balochistan has a limited share in CPEC projects. According to the official figure available on CPEC web-portal, out of 10 completed energy projects (with an estimated cost of US\$10.14 billion), only energy project - Hubco Coal Power project worth US\$1.912 billion - is located in Balochistan (Planning Commission of Pakistan 2020). Furthermore, out of seven under-construction projects (worth US\$10.3 billion), only one energy project - Hubco Thar Coal power plant (worth US\$497.7) - is located in Balochistan. In contrast, seven energy projects worth US\$7.43 billion have already been completed in Sindh and two energy projects worth US\$3.82 billion have been completed in Punjab. In addition, one major CPEC-related infrastructure project Lahore Orange-Line rail-based mass transit project (worth US\$1.62 billion) also located in Punjab.

Furthermore, the issue of Balochistan’s share in the fruits of Gwadar port is pouring more fuel to the fire. Some Baloch leaders view Gwadar port project “as a scheme to steal their real estate than as a means to strengthen the local economy (Markey 2020b, viii).” The reason for growing concerns about Gwadar port emerge from the fact that under the operational management contract of Gwadar port, 91 per cent of revenue generated from the port will go to “China Overseas Port Holding Company (COPHC)” and the remaining 9 per cent will go to federal government of Pakistan (Asia Times, April 25, 2018). Additionally, for Gwadar port project, the federal government has also allowed a 23-year tax exemption to the COPHC (Nikkei Asian Review, October 13, 2019). The 23-year tax exemption to COPHC means that the provincial government of Balochistan, where Gwadar port is located, will get nothing from the revenues.

Under such circumstances, the provincial government of Balochistan has repeatedly objected against federal government’s highly centralized CPEC-related decision-making and also against the asymmetries in project-related resource distribution. For instance, in December 2018, Chief Minister of Balochistan, Jam Kamal complained on the floor of provincial assembly that “Balochistan’s current share under CPEC investment is only 4.5 per cent...and if we don’t include Gwadar port and

Hubco projects, then Balochistan's share in CPEC is meager one per cent (Dawn, December 21, 2018)." In December 2018, Balochistan's provincial assembly adopted a resolution demanding that the federal government should constitute a national commission to investigate the disproportionate distribution of CPEC-related resources and projects (Dawn, December 21, 2018). In February 2020, Abdul Malik Baloch, the former Chief Minister of Balochistan, complained about the lack of Baloch representation in CPEC-related job opportunities and demanded that the federal government should prioritize the inclusion of local Baloch communities in all CPEC projects being executed in the province (Dawn, February 10, 2020).

Federal government's approach towards the implementation of CPEC in Balochistan in terms of not giving the province its due share in the economic benefits of CPEC and lack of job opportunities for the local Baloch population, has been further fueling the fears of marginalization in Balochistan. Many Baloch political leaders maintain the view that if the federal government would continue to ignore the Baloch people in CPEC and Gwadar port projects, it will only result in the strengthening of the narrative of hardliner Baloch leaders that federal government is more interested in exploiting the resources of Balochistan.

Balochistan is not the only disgruntled critic of CPEC. Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) is another region where local concerns are growing over the exclusion from the fruits of CPEC. Although CPEC opens avenues for the socio-economic development in Pakistan, the local residents of GB are skeptical about the prospects of CPEC-related economic development in their region. Their skepticism derives from the fact that GB region has very limited share in CPEC-related industrialization and hydropower projects. For instance, GB region has abundance of water resources and considered to be "a sustainable 'white goldmine', with a recoverable potential of over 100,000 MW of clean hydropower at roughly 2 cents per Kw/h (Howe and Hunzai 2019, 17)." But despite GB's immense potential for hydropower generation, the region has been fully excluded from CPEC-related hydropower projects. Currently, only one project, Gilgit KIU hydropower, has been listed as a potential CPEC project in GB (not confirmed project) on the official CPEC web-portal.

Within the milieu of CPEC, the absence of GB region from Pakistan's constitutional and federal decision-making bodies such as the National Assembly, Senate, Council of Common Interests (CCI), Senate Standing Committee on CPEC, and recently created CPEC Authority, is the key reason behind their grievances (Shafique and Iftikhar 2017,

21-22). For the people of GB, attaining any kind of benefit from CPEC is closely linked to the issue of region's constitutional status – that is the incorporation of GB into the federation of Pakistan as a constitutional province. But because of their absence from Pakistan's constitutional and other federal decision-making bodies, the people of the region almost have no say in CPEC-related decision-making and ultimately limited space to lobby for their share in project-related investments.

The absence of the GB region from Pakistan's constitutional and decision-making bodies has not only been contested by the people of GB but also by Pakistan's mainstream political parties such as PPP. In 2016, legislators from PPP visited GB and “condemned the Senate Special Committee on CPEC for not addressing the concerns of GB residents on the constitutional status of the region (Ahmed, 2019, p. 408).” Similarly, in 2018, Farhatullah Babar, a Senator from PPP, criticized the federal government of Pakistan for exploiting the natural resources of GB but not granting economic and political rights to its people (*The News*, May16, 2018). While speaking to local seminar on human rights, Senator Babar said: “the people of GB pay all taxes, they are issued Pakistani CNICs and passports and also recruited in the army but were denied representation in the national parliament (*The News*, May16, 2018).” There have been long-

term demands from GB residents calling on the federal government to declare GB as a constitutional province of Pakistan (Shafique and Iftikhar 2017, p. 24; Howe and Hunzai, 2019, p. 17). The GB region provides the only land-based connection between China and Pakistan and thus holds fundamental importance for the implementation and success of CPEC. Thus, the government of Pakistan must pay special attention to address the grievances of GB residents by fulfilling their longstanding constitutional demands.

The above presented analysis illustrates that after five years of its launch, CPEC continues to be a source of contention in center-province and inter-province relations. Regardless of the state's efforts to quell regional and/or provincial disagreements, there are still problems to be resolved and a need for concentrated state efforts to continuously address the grievances of small provinces. On the issue of equitable distribution of CPEC resources, as a first step, it is imperative for the federal government of Pakistan to address the grievances of small provinces. Instead of creating parallel decision-making bodies such as CPEC Authority, the federal government must take all CPEC-related decisions in CCI by involving all the provinces (including the GB region) in the decision-making process and share all important information related to the agreements with the provincial governments. Pakistan's federal

government must pay a special focus to address the grievances of Balochistan province. A first step in this direction would be to determine a special job quota and employment opportunities for the local Baloch people to alleviate their grievances. The socio-economic development is essential for Balochistan which is severely affected by ethnic, sociopolitical, and sectarian cleavages. Furthermore, the federal government of Pakistan must grant equal political and economic rights to the people of GB, allow the representatives of GB to participate in the meetings of CCI and other federal decision-making institutions, and give GB an equal share in CPEC projects and resources.

Conclusion

In Pakistan, CPEC sustains the image of a 'game changer' project that would supercharge Pakistan's fragile and decaying economy and usher a new era of socioeconomic development and political stability in the country. But a careful analysis of the initial five years of CPEC demonstrate that the initiative has failed to become the transformative force as it was originally promoted. The analysis presented in this paper demonstrates that the way in which CPEC is currently being implanted, has brought several challenges detrimental to Pakistan's macroeconomic and sociopolitical stability.

On the economic front, CPEC has contributed in worsening the macroeconomic disequilibrium in Pakistan. Soaring debt burden, ballooning

trade deficit, and worsening current account crisis are the major CPEC-related implications for Pakistan's macro-economic stability. On the political front, deteriorating centre-province relations, disagreement between the federating units over the distribution of CPEC-related investment and allocation of energy and infrastructure projects, and intensifying ethnic tendencies in Balochistan and GB region are some of the untoward fallouts of CPEC that could possibly undermine the domestic stability in Pakistan.

To overcome these challenges, as a first step, Pakistan must re-evaluate CPEC agreements to safeguard the country's economic and political interests. It should renegotiate with China to realign CPEC projects, initiate the development of SEZs on priority basis and include agricultural cooperation in project's official portfolio. Pakistan's trade deficit with China is one of the key reasons for Islamabad's worsening external-sector imbalances. The inclusion of agricultural sector in CPEC could provide Pakistan a massive opportunity to mend its trade deficit with China by increasing its agriculture related exports to China's lucrative markets. Moreover, Pakistan needs to initiate structural reforms to manage its chronic current account crisis. Pakistan's external borrowing and import-led growth strategy (with CPEC being the lynchpin) as well as its poor performance in the export sector are the drivers

of its perpetual balance of payment crisis. Therefore, instead of relying heavily on foreign loan and/or aid to finance large scale projects like CPEC, Pakistan needs to create an investment friendly environment to attract foreign direct investments (FDI) which unlike foreign borrowings (including BRI and IMF loans) and/or aid, involves a certain degree of risk-sharing with the investors.

Second, it is imperative for the federal government of Pakistan to address the grievances of small provinces particularly related to CPEC implementation. The federal government must discuss all CPEC-related decisions in the CCI and involve all the provinces (including the GB region) in the decision-making process and share all important information related to the agreements with the provincial governments. Pakistan's federal government must also address the grievances of Balochistan province. To address the grievances of local Baloch nationalists, Islamabad should allocate a special quota in CPEC-related investment for Balochistan and guarantee employment opportunities for local Baloch to alleviate their grievances. Moreover, instead of employing non-Baloch labor in Gwadar and other development projects, federal government must initiate special skill development programs in Balochistan to prepare local Baloch for CPEC-related jobs. Finally, the federal government of Pakistan must grant equal

political and economic rights to the people of GB, allow the people of GB to participate in the meetings of CCI and other federal decision-making institutions, and give GB an equal share in CPEC projects and resources.

CPEC is the "flagship project" and the only bilateral venture among the six economic corridors of the BRI. The success of CPEC will enhance China's credibility that the BRI is equally beneficial for all the participating countries. Given this, China needs to address the concerns of the participant countries by ensuring transparency in project-related terms and conditions, evaluating the costs and risks of the projects, devising a workable debt sustainability framework, and complying with international rules of infrastructure development. A more transparent strategy will help China and the participant countries to subdue the shortcomings of the BRI. Similarly, the participant countries must also take special care of their national interests before finalizing the BRI-related deals. Instead of relying heavily on China's guarantees and/or expectations, participant countries must also pay special focus on conducting cost-benefit analysis before embracing any project. Undoubtedly, the BRI presents a lucrative opportunity for many countries to achieve rapid economic growth through infrastructure development. Yet, China needs to understand that the BRI could not

become a reality at the cost of other countries sovereignty and national integrity.

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